

Preparation of New Fluorine Containing 2-Phenylindole Derivatives as Antifertility Agents

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New fluorine containing 2-(2/4'-hydroxyphenyl)indoles (1) have been synthesised by Fischer indole synthesis. (1) reacts with *N,N*-dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride to give basic ether residue in the 2/4-position of the 2-phenyl ring. Representative compounds have been screened for antifertility activity at 10 mg/kg P.C. (oral).

OF the various heterocyclic systems studied for their use as antifertility agents, 2,3-diarylindoles^{1,2}, 3,4-diarylchromans³, 2,3-diarylbenzothiophenes⁴ and their hydroxy and alkoxy derivatives^{5,6} showed promising activity. A phenyl ring at 2-position of indole was reported to increase antifertility activity. These compounds possess (i) an aryl ethylene pattern in their structure which is known to exert a marked effect on the mammalian reproductive system⁷, (ii) a methoxy group which can be considered as a counterpart of the oxygen atom in the 3-position of steroids, and (iii) a similarity of molecular structure with the rigid A/B ring system of steroids⁸. In view of these observations, we have synthesised several new 2-(2/4'-hydroxyphenyl)indoles (1) and 2-(2/4'-*N,N*-dialkylaminoethoxyphenyl)indoles (2) as possible antifertility agents.

Results and Discussion

2/4-Hydroxyacetophenone was treated with phenylhydrazine at 60-70° to give the corresponding hydrazone, which was cyclised with PPA at 125-50° to give 1. Appearance of broad signal due to NH and OH at 3350-3500 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra indicated

the formation of 1, which was further confirmed by ¹H nmr and mass spectra. In ¹H nmr spectra, all aromatic protons resonated at δ 6.4-8.0. The NH and OH signals were observed at δ 7.8-8.1 and 4.5-5.0, respectively. In its mass spectrum, the molecular ion peak (*M*⁺) was observed at *m/z* 227 (1a).

Compounds 2 were obtained by refluxing 2-(2/4'-hydroxyphenyl)indole with *N,N*-dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride in dry acetone (Scheme 1). Disappearance of OH at 3440 and appearance of CH₂ at 3160-3280 cm⁻¹ in ir spectra indicated the formation of 2. In ¹H nmr spectra, the signals due to OCH₂, CH₂N(CH₂)₂ and CH₂-CH₂-CH₂ were observed at δ 3.9-4.2, 2.3-2.8, 1.3-1.7 for piperidinoethoxy; OCH₂, CH₂-O-CH₂, CH₂N(CH₂)₂ at 4.3-4.5, 3.6-4.0, 3.3-3.6 for morpholinoethoxy and OCH₂, CH₂N(CH₂)₂, CH₂-CH₂ at 4.2-4.5, 3.3-3.9 and 1.7-2.2, respectively for pyrrolidinoethoxy groups.

Antifertility activity: 2a-d, k and l were screened for their antifertility activity in adult female rats of Charles Foster strain at 10 mg/kg P.C. (oral) and they showed promising results.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 2-PHENYLINDOLE DERIVATIVES (1 AND 2)

Compd.	X	Y	OH/OCH ₂ CH ₂ NR ₂	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	N% : Found/(Calcd.)
1a	5-F	H	4-OH	225	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ FNO	6.00 (6.17)
b	6-F	H	4-OH	210	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ FNO	6.20 (6.17)
c	5-F	F	4-OH	225	50	C ₁₄ H ₉ F ₂ NO	5.58 (5.71)
d	H	H	2-OH	160	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO	6.56 (6.70)
e	H	H	4-OH	230	53	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO	6.64 (6.70)
2a	5-F	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	203	54	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O	8.12 (8.28)
b	5-F	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	148	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O	8.58 (8.64)
c	5-F	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	165	60	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O ₂	8.21 (8.28)
d	6-F	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	192	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O	8.70 (8.64)
e	6-F	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	168	55	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O	8.15 (8.28)
f	6-F	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	182	60	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O	8.12 (8.28)
g	5-F	F	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	150	45	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ F ₂ N ₂ O	8.15 (8.18)
h	H	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	114	58	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O	8.92 (9.15)
i	H	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	188	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O	8.68 (8.75)
j	H	H	4-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	173	60	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	8.71 (8.75)
k	H	H	2-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	188	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O	9.05 (9.15)
l	H	H	2-OCH ₂ CH ₂ N	109	58	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	8.60 (8.75)

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets, ¹H nmr spectra were recorded

on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The purity of all compounds was routinely checked by tlc.

2-Fluorophenyl acetate : This compound was prepared by a new low temperature method, as the

earlier method of Minor and Vander Werf⁸ that involved a high temperature and was time consuming. To a solution of 2-fluorophenol (28.0 g, 0.25 mol) in sodium hydroxide solution (160 ml, 10%) were added acetic anhydride (22.0 ml, 0.3 mol) and crushed ice (175 g), and the mixture was shaken well for 5 min. The product was extracted with carbon tetrachloride, and purified by distillation (25.9 g, 92.5%), b.p. 190° (lit.⁸ b.p. 190-92°).

3-Fluoro-4-hydroxyacetophenone : It was prepared following the method of Minor and Vanderwerf⁸ using 2-fluorophenyl acetate (15.4 g, 0.1 mol), anhydrous aluminium chloride (16 g) and dry carbon disulphide (25 ml).

3/4-Fluorophenylhydrazine : 3/4-Fluorophenylhydrazine was prepared following the method of Suschitzky⁹ from 3/4-fluoroaniline.

5-Fluoro-2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)indole (1a) : 4-Fluorophenylhydrazine (12.6 g, 0.1 mol) was heated with 4-hydroxyacetophenone (13.6 g, 0.1 mol) on a steam-bath for 30 min. The resultant phenylhydrazone was heated with freshly prepared PPA (4.8 g) at 125-50°, when cyclisation took place with the evolution of white fumes. The resultant product was cooled, poured into crushed ice, the mixture left for 4-5 h, and then filtered and crystallised from benzene to furnish **1a** (6.9 g, 55%), m.p. 225° (Found : N, 6.00. C₁₄H₁₀FNO requires N, 6.17%).

Compounds **1b-e**, prepared similarly, are listed in Table 1 along with their physical and analytical data.

5-Fluoro-2-(4'-β-piperidinoethoxyphenyl)indole (2a) : A mixture of 5-fluoro-2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)indole

(2.2 g, 0.01 mol), piperidinoethyl chloride hydrochloride (2.0 g, 0.011 mol) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (5 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml) for 24 h, cooled, filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was recrystallised from acetone to afford **2a** (1.0 g, 54%), m.p. 203° (Found : N, 8.12. C₂₁H₂₃FN₂O requires N, 8.28%).

Compounds **2b-1** were also prepared in a similar way. Their physical and analytical characteristics are recorded in Table 1.

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